

The Portrait of the Tirta Agung Tourism Village as a Geological Tourist Destination: The Case of Ijen Geopark in Bondowoso, Indonesia

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ABSTRACT: The aim of this study is to analyze the implementation of Tirta Agung Tourism Village, Sukosari Kidul Village, Sumberwringin District, Bondowoso in supporting the development of Ijen Geopark. The research uses a constructivist paradigm with a qualitative approach with domain analysis, share vision, participation, networking, and collaboration. The analysis is carried out by qualitative descriptive methods. The subjects of the study were the Head of the Tourism Awareness Group, the Chairman of the Ijen Geopark Daily, the Head of the Sports and Sports Youth Tourism Office, several informants related to the implementation of the Tirta Agung tourism village. The results showed that the implementation of tourism villages refers to the regulations of the local government and village apparatus through BUMDes and Pokdarwis. The implementation of tirta Agung tourism village, Sukosari village, can run well. through the traditional communication model of local wisdom, village youth gatherings while drinking coffee, managing stakeholder support, and maintaining group compliance.

KEYWORDS: Community Empowerment, Geopark, Strategy Implementation, Tourism Village.

INTRODUCTION

The Bondowoso Regency has designated and proposed the Mount Ijen area as a World Geopark by submitting a dossier to UNESCO and obtaining approval for the development of the Ijen Geopark since 2021. The regional tourism area development strategy is carried out by determining four Regency Tourism Strategic Areas (KSPK), namely: (1) KSPK Raung Ijen; (2) KSPK Solor; (3) KSPK Argopuro; and (4) KSPK Magalitikum (Bondowoso Regency Regional Regulation, No. 3 of 2019). Based on the determination of the four KSPK, the priority in the development of tourism villages is the Raung Ijen KSPK. In the KSPK Raung Ijen area, the focus and locus of community development includes three sub-districts, namely: Ijen, Sumberwringin, and Cermee districts. Tirta Agung Tourism is one of the tourist destinations in the KSPK Ijen Raung Geopark.

The development of the Ijen Geopark is directed to strengthen the potential of the Ijen Raung geopark, which includes three pillars, namely: (1) Geology Diversity; 2) Biology Diversity; and 3) Cultural Diversity. These three pillars are supported by their sustainable use and provide feedback for the welfare of the community in a sustainable manner. Development targets are implemented through a program to strengthen aspects that include: (a) Preservation of nature and culture; (b) Education; (c) Community Empowerment; and (d) Tourism. Therefore, the role of human resources is the main capital as a driver as well as implementing the management of local potential and resources in their area.

Figure 1: Model Tourism Development of Ijen Geopark Bondowoso
Source: Modified

Institutional preparation in the development of the Ijen Geopark, the Regent of Bondowoso formed the Daily Management of the Ijen Geopark (Decree of the Regent of Bondowoso Indonesia, No. 188.45/250/430.4.2/2021). The Daily Management is in charge of executing plans for Ijen Geopark development activities. The strengthening of human resources is being handled by the Youth Culture and Sports Tourism Office and the Bondowoso District Education Office. The efforts of the local government in the development of Ijen Geopark are to encourage the collaboration of village Triple Helix in empowerment and foster community participation through the development of superior tourism villages.

The study was conducted at Tirta Agung tourism, Sukosari Kidul village, Sumberwringin District, as a tourist village destination in KSPK Ijen Raung. Tirta Agung tourism village only operated in 2018 managed by BUMDes Makmur Sejahtera together with Pokdarwis Sukosari village. Tirta Agung Tourism was inaugurated in 2019 by the Regent of Bondowoso and was determined based on the Decree of the Regent of Bondowoso No. 188.45/329/430.4.2/2019. In the decree, it was stipulated that: a) Sukosari Kidul Village, Sumberwringin district, as a tourist village under the name "Tirta Agung" Tourism Village; b) in order to increase tourist visits, tourist attractions as referred to in the First dictum to be promoted through printed and electronic media, which are technically fostered and facilitated by the Regional Apparatus in charge, Villages, and Tourism; c) to support the economy of rural communities, tourist attraction managers as referred to in the First dictum in order to optimize the resources and superior products available.

Based on the regulations and policies for the determination of Tirta Agung tourism villages that regulate so the managers can take advantage of the tourism potential in their area, optimize resources, and superior products that available. This policy is an opportunity and at the same time a challenge for tourism village managers, namely BUMDes and Pokdarwis of Sukosari Kidul village. Therefore, the problem in this study is how the implementation of the Tirta Agung tourism village in the development of the Ijen Geopark Bondowoso area. The development of Tirta Agung tourism village not only has the responsibility of advancing

the potential of tourist attractions in the village, but has demands to synergize with other components in the development of KSPK Ijen Raung Geopark.

Sustainable Tourism Development and Community Based Tourism

Ijen Tourism is one of the volcanological tourist destinations with the charm of blue fire from the crater of Mount Ijen and traditional sulfur miners. In addition, the Ijen Mountain area also has a wealth of biology diversity, especially the coffee plant area on the slopes of the Ijen mountains and Mount Raung. Another charm is the rich cultural anthropology of megalithic relics in the form of megalithic sites scattered in several areas of Bondowoso. All these tourism assets require management by local governments and communities by developing the principles of sustainable tourism.

The concept of sustainable tourism development, provides several initiatives that can be taken by the public sector to regulate the growth of tourism to be better and put sustainable tourism as a priority because good tourism efforts can protect sources that are important for tourism not only for now but in the future (Sunarta and Arida, 2017). As the concept of sustainable development which contains the main elements, namely development that aims to always develop potential towards good and sustainable conditions, representing the meaning of resilience and sustainability (Cristian, *et al.*, 2015).

One of the relevant concepts in supporting and providing space for the development of sustainable tourism is the concept of geoparks from UNESCO Global Geoparks. Geopark is a bottom up aspect, an approach to the community related to aspects of conservation, education and sustainable development, providing opportunities for geoparks to cooperate and develop built attractions, infrastructure that supports sustainable development around attractions (Briggs, *et al.*, 2021). In planning tourism destinations, a community-based tourism approach (CBT) can be a mainstay to accelerate the growth and development of tourist areas. Community-based tourism is a mainstay to accelerate the growth and development of tourist areas (ASEAN, 2015).

Village Triple Helix Concept

The triple helix model was first introduced by Etzkowitz & Leydesdorff (1995), which is an approach to create cooperation from three actors, namely: Academics, business, and government. The triple helix function is divided into the process of establishing well-being, generating knowledge and normative supervision (Leydesdorff, 2012; Cai & Amaral, 2021). While the village triple helix model includes three components of the system in rural areas. Operational definition of all three village triple helix subsystems (Widjajani, *et al.*, 2015), be: (1) Village Industrial Subsystem, is a system consisting of small village industries or home industries, and the supply chain of these industries, including small industrial entrepreneurs, craftsmen, raw material suppliers, marketers and so on; (2) The Village Government Subsystem is a system that includes village government institutions and related officials such as Village Officers, Village Chief, BUMDes, Pokdarwis, and (3) Village Education Subsystem, is a system related to formal, informal, and nonformal educational institutions, as well as people who can get education (younger generation, ordinary people, school students, and so on).

The empowerment of the village triple helix component is directed so that village communities can understand the concept and context of problems in triple helix interaction and collaboration (Herliana, 2015; Hamsani & Khairiyansyah, 2018). It needs further follow-up so that slowly but surely the realization of the synergy of the village triple helix subsystem that really shows the output and outcome of presenting a tourism destination that increasingly displays an interesting charm to visit.

Construction of Tourism Village in Bondowoso Regency

Law No. 10 of 2009 concerning Tourism mandates that tourism development is necessary to encourage equitable distribution of business opportunities and obtain benefits and be able to face the challenges of changing local, national, and global life. Therefore, the Regent and regional apparatus as elements of local government administration, needs to take tourism policy measures in their regions through the development of regional tourism development strategies.

According to Nuryanti in Yuliati and Suwandono (2016) Tourism Village is a form of integration between attractions, accommodation, and supporting facilities presented in a structure of community life that is integrated with applicable procedures and traditions. One of the economic empowerment of the people in the field of tourism is through the development of tourism villages. A tourist village is a tourist destination area or also called a tourism destination, which integrates tourist attractions, public facilities, tourism facilities, accessibility, which are presented in a structure of community life that is integrated with applicable procedures and traditions (Law No. 10 of 2009). In the concept of green tourism villages that emphasize more on efforts to optimize existing development resources. Through this concept, it pays more attention to the village community as a life entity to be

encouraged not only as an object of development, but it requires cross-sectoral and cross-regional planning and development with the aim of achieving sustainable and inclusive tourism development without negatively impacting the environment and local culture.

The implementation of tourism village development is realized by providing tourist facilities to carry out a tourist activity that can cause economic, social and cultural impacts or consequences as well as the preservation of the natural environment of the countryside. Implementation is the process of realising a program to show its results (Jones in Mulyadi, 2015). It is further stated that implementation is also a general process of administrative action that can be researched at a certain program level (Grindle in Mulyadi, 2015).

The implementation stage is an important thing to measure the extent of the success of a program, so at the stage there needs to be supervision and evaluation in order to achieve the goals that have been set together. This stage requires consistency and cooperation from all stakeholders who play a role in the success of the tourism village program by building good communication and cooperation, so that every element or element involved in it can carry out its duties and functions so that the objectives of the tourism village program can be achieved (Padabain and Nugroho, 2018).

The Bodowoso District Government has settled out strategic steps through the drafting of RIPPARDA (Regional Tourism Development Master Plan) Bondowoso District. RIPPARDA is a district/city of tourism, development planning document for a period of 15-25 years (Permenpar RI No. 10 of 2016). The various scopes of planning and the steps for their realization will be largely determined by the implementation of the strategy implementation contained in the RIPPARDA that has been prepared.

Public Policy Collaboration and Implementation

Public Policy Collaboration is a collaborative process to transmit ideas and solve problems together towards a common vision or goal. Good collaboration and harmonious walking are the keys to the birth of creative thinking. Collaboration that goes smoothly will be something that is very important to achieve the best results when solving problems. Collaboration in addition to occurring within the organization internally, collaboration can also occur across sectors in networks and partnerships (Bryson, Crosby, & Stone, 2015; O'Leary & Vij, 2012).

Forms of collaborative governance to address various problems in society can involve relevant stakeholders in creating policy and service innovations in an effort to find the best solution (Cinar, Trott, & Simms, 2019). Wanna (2008), states that in collaborative governance, there are 4 (four) that must be implemented in collaboration, namely, are; (1) share vision; (2) participation (stakeholder involvement); (3) building networks (good relationships occur); and (4) collaboration (establishing partnerships between the stakeholders involved). Policy implementation in principle is a way for a policy to achieve its goals, implementation is a process of activities carried out by various actors so that in the end it will get an outcome that is in accordance with the goals or objectives of the policy itself (Pramono, 2020). Barbara Gray in London (<http://www.scottlondon.com>). Saying the final step of the collaborative process is the implementation phase in which 1) participating groups or organizations deal with their constituents; 2) the parties gather support from those who will be tasked with implementing the agreement; 3) the structure for implementation is established; and finally 4) agreements are monitored and compliance is ensured.

METHODOLOGY

This research uses the paradigm of constructivism to understand the perspective and focus and problems of the research by looking at social phenomena; conducting direct observations and interviews with actors in the framework of the scientific process; collecting documentation materials and others as tourist activities developed by the local community (Bungin, 2017). The research was conducted in the Tirta Agung tourism village, and the subjects of the study/participants included: Head of the Tourism Awareness Group (Pokdarwis), Chairman of the Ijen Geopark Bondowoso Daily, Head of Tourism of the Youth and Sports Tourism Office, several informants related to the implementation of the Tirta Agung tourism village. Based on the paradigm of constructivism, the paradigmatic views used are: (1) social phenomena are analyzed based on their meaning; (2) using observation in understanding social phenomena; (3) conduct an understanding of all social phenomena that have a relationship with all research data through in-depth interviews (Denzin and Lincoln; 2009), research using qualitative methods (Creswell, 2016). The analysis technique used is a qualitative descriptive analysis to analyse and describe domains related to the implementation of the Tirta Agung tourism village. The domains analyzed include: (1) Implementation of building a common vision; (2) Pioneering and managing stakeholder participation); (3) building a network of relationships and promotions; and (4) develop stakeholder partnerships.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Tirta Agung Tourism which is located in the village of Sukosari Kidul, Sumberwringin District, is located in West Sokleh Hamlet RT 18 / RW05. Tirta Agung Tourism is managed by BUMDes Makmur Sejahtera, with President Director Hadin Fadiri, S.Pd. Operationally the management of objects and tourist attractions is handled by Tourism Awareness Groups (Pokdarwis) which are located in East Sokleh Hamlet Village RT 20 / RW05 Sukosari Kidul Village, Sumberwringin subdistrict, Bondowoso Regency. The Chairman of Tourism Awareness Groups Tirta Agung Tourism is M. Fadil Susanto, SH.

Tabel 1. Tirta Agung Tourism Products and Facilities

Main objects and attractions	Tirta Agung Tour Package	Amenity
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Culinary floating gazebo ❖ Fish Therapy (foot therapy) ❖ Feeding fish ❖ Swimming Pool of Natural Springs (child and adult) ❖ Water bike games ❖ Fishing garden ❖ Home Meeting (hall) ❖ Camping ground and Outbond ❖ Event area ❖ Agro Tourism ❖ Handicrafts (Handmade) Udheng, Keychain, Bamboo Crafts 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Feeding fish, ❖ Culinary pedesan, ❖ Family Ghatering, ❖ Booking meeting places, ❖ Photography Services, ❖ Enjoying Sunset, ❖ Cultural Traditions, ❖ Jaran Kencak, ❖ Singo Ulung, ❖ Hadrah. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Homestay ❖ Parking Lot ❖ Complete Toilet ❖ Mushola ❖ Health facilities ❖ Event Area

Source: Chairman of Tourism Awareness Group (Pokdarwis) Tirta Agung

Tirta Agung Tourism Products

Like a tourism destination that presents superior tourism products, ease of accessibility, and completeness of amenities. Tirta Agung tourism village, which is based on nature and rural environment, offers objects and attractions that utilize and make natural potential as an interesting and unique attraction that is created and packed with superior beauty, beauty, and creative benefits. The Chairman of Pokdarwis of Tirta Agung Tourism Village (2022) stated:

... Tirta Agung tourism village aims to empower existing human resources and natural resources so that the existence of this tourism village can be known and recognized by the wider community, so that it can create its own image for tourists who come to enjoy the rural atmosphere in our region. The facilities and rides we provide to provide service and satisfaction to visitors.

Activity	Object	Description	View
Recreational Tourism	Swimming Pool of Natural Springs	Kid & Family Recreation	
Culinary	Floating café	Enjoy culinary with the concept of floating café	
Water exercise	Swimming pool	Sport & Recreation	
Children's park	Photo spots	Photo spots for children and families	

Figure 4: Objects and Attractions of Tirta Agung Tourism Village

Source: Chairman of Tourism Awareness Group (Pokdarwis) Tirta Agung

Activity	Object	Description	View
Outbond Education	Outbond & Educational activities	Scout activities	
Adventures outbond	Outbond tourism	Outbond experience	
Meeting	Meeting Hall	Meeting activities in a relaxed atmosphere	
Parking lot	Travel complementary services	Spacious and adequate parking location	
Souvenir	Handmade crafts	Handicrafts Key chains, Bamboo Handicrafts	

Figure 5: Objects and Attractions of Tirta Agung Tourism Village
Source: Chairman of Tourism Awareness Group (Pokdarwis) Tirta Agung

Implementation of Building a Common Vision

Tourism development is recognized by many parties as having positive benefits for smoking and the welfare of the community. Nevertheless, the development of tourism can also have a negative impact on the environment. Therefore, the government and the Regional Apparatus in charge, the Village Government, and related stakeholders build a common vision in the field of tourism development.

Activity	Object	Description	Education	View
Tourism Awareness Groups	Village Youth	Character Building	Education & Training	
Workshop	Local Government	Village Government Briefing on Business Licensing	Scientific, Education & Geotourism	
Workshop	Local Government	Village Government Briefing for the importance of reducing air pollution	Education & Eco-tourism	
Workshop	Local Government	Briefing and improvement of geopark	Education & Geopark	

Figure 5: Activities to Build a Shared Vision of Tourism
Source: Chairman of the Daily Management of Ijen Geopark Bondowoso Region

The Bondowoso Government through the Youth and Sports Tourism Office always provides support, guidance, and provides the facilities needed for the development of the Tirta Agung tourist village. The Head of the Youth and Sports Tourism Office (2022) stated:

... related to the village government system, which has autonomy in regulating government in its territory through village apparatus according to the structure in the village government system. BUMDes as part of the village government system have an important function and role in the development of tourism policies and strategies. The purpose of BUMDes as in Permendes No. 4/2015 is to improve the village economy, increase community efforts in managing the economic potential of the village. In the field of tourism, Pokdarwis always encourages the public to be able to create creative and innovative products, competitive because they have product characteristics and peculiarities. Routinely conduct coaching and provide assistance in the form of Pokdarwis operational equipment and provide grants for homestay equipment..

The Daily Management of Ijen Geopark also collaborates in empowering the community to be able to participate and jointly realize the development of Ijen Geopark in the field of tourism through tourism villages in Tirta Agung. The Chairman of the Daily Management of Ijen Geopark (2022) stated:

“... Villages in the Ijen Geopark area are spread across 14 districts, one of which is Sukosari Kidul village, Sumberwringin District, which is located in the Ijen Raung KSPK, which has now been operationalized tirta Agung tourism activities. We always coordinate with the village and Pokdarwis to make Tirta Agung tourism as the spearhead of developing community participation in tourism village activities so as to support the development of Ijen Geopark. The role of the Sukosari Kidul village government and BUMDes together with Pokdarwis and the private sector to continue to innovate to create superior tourist villages..

The role of village government is dominant because it is the party that has the authority to manage rural areas and the potential of local villages. Growing awareness of rural communities for participation through education and creative economy efforts. The results of the interview with the Chairman of the Sukosari Village Tourism Awareness Group, said:

... The development of tourism villages begins with the initiation of village youth who yearn for the movement to serve the village, then conduct cross-party discussions facilitated by the Village Head. Planning for the construction of community-based tourist attractions managed by BUMDes with Pokdarwis. We conducted a comparative study to developed tourist attractions as a consideration in developing superior tourist villages. We take advantage of the tradition of gathering over coffee together to build inspiration, imagination to form the uniqueness of the tourist village and build the right organizational strategy..

The idea of village development was initiated by the village youth and received a response and was facilitated by the village government. This shows that there is a very strong foundation for the implementation of tourism villages, so that in realizing the plan to develop objects and tourist attractions can run smoothly. As for the main considerations in designing the appearance of tourist attractions, the Chairman of the Tourism Awareness Group, stated:

... we thought how to rise from the slump when BUMDes with the savings and loans business experienced a state of colaps, So we see the potential for the development of tourist villages because we have natural potential that is suitable as a tourist attraction. We realize to innovate so that economic potential development solutions can touch all levels of rural society by encouraging participation in the development of village-based tourism. We are grateful when the community develops its creativity and facilitates community empowerment programs.

Pioneering and managing stakeholder participation

Stakeholder participation is very important in advancing the Tirta Agung tourist village located in KSPK Ijen Raung. The manager always communicates and coordinates with the Daily Management of Ijen Geopark, academics and practitioners whose cooperation is built by the Youth and Sports Tourism Office to provide assistance and empowerment to the community in the Tirta Agung tourism village. The Head of the Youth and Sports Tourism Office (2022) stated:

... Tourism office provides assistance through cooperation with penta helix elements, such as academics and practitioners to provide the necessary assistance and empowerment. In addition, it also helps promote the potential of tourism villages through social media and digital content..

The role of active participation of local communities in the planning and development of Ijen Geopark is an important priority according to the main pillars of the geopark. Therefore, the empowerment of local communities, including those in Tirta

Agung tourism village, the focus and locus of development activities for the Ijen Geopark. Chairman of the Daily Management of Ijen Geopark (2022) stated:

... villages in the Ijen Geopark area are spread across 14 sub-districts, so the potential for local villages and regions is very significant to be driven to support the development of Ijen Geopark. The village governments in the 14 sub-districts can be the spearhead in supporting the local government program to realize the Ijen Geopark in a mutualistic symbiotic manner. We always work together through formal and nonformal education channels, community groups, village industrial business groups, and through BUMDes businesses with Pokdarwis and other private sector..

Pokdarwis is a tourism driving group at the village level that has an informal institutional form, formed from community members in the village area. Pokdarwis has an important role in developing and realising Tourism Awareness and Sapta Charm in their area. The role and contribution of Pokdarwis is very much needed, both in quality and quantity in helping to support the development and growth of its tourism village destinations. Chief of Pokdarwis tourism village Tirta Agung (2022) said:

... in building participation we go to community leaders to ask for support and guidance in mapping the potential resources of local residents who will be involved in the development of tourism villages. After we get information from community leaders, then we go to the parties that will be involved such as, craftsmen of local products, culinary, convection, local cultural arts, as well as providing display facilities for marketing and interaction space with visitors. In maintaining the sustainability of cooperation we create galleries and mutually beneficial cooperation agreements. We always invite partners to continue innovating and developing creativity in order to maintain the competitiveness and excellence of Tirta Agung tourism village.

Developing Stakeholder Partnerships

Tirta Agung Tourism Village located in the Ijen Raung KSPK Geopark, so the spirit of developing the Tirta Agung tourism village is related to the development of the Ijen Geopark in the Bondowoso area. In accordance with the pillars of geopark development, which include; preservation of nature and culture, education, community empowerment, and tourism, the presence of Tirta Agung tourism can be part of the development of the Ijen Bodowoso Geopark Area. Head of the Tourism Awareness Group, stated:

“...The purpose of developing tourism in the Ijen Geopark economically is how to make the length of stay and spending of money for visitors in Bondowoso. Bondowoso regional government focuses on tourism villages in the Ijen Geopark area, as well as villages in the Ijen Geopark delineation. We focus on two things, namely the tourism service business and the creative economy. The system implemented can be through individuals or groups recommended by the village government. The local government wants to provide the widest possible benefit to the community directly. We always facilitate the needs of the tourism village community through partnerships needed by the community..

The Daily Management of Ijen Geopark as the authority that coordinates stakeholder partnerships approaches the penta helix element and the village triple helix institution. Make MoUs and cooperation institutionally, and implement agreed programs. Monitoring and evaluation activities are carried out jointly and the results are discussed together in regular meetings, for control and necessary improvements. The Chairman of the Daily Management of the Ijen Geopark bondowoso region (in 2022) stated:

... We focus on community empowerment, amenity development, human resources, and digitalization. Currently, we are developing digital promotions, paperless publications, tourism working tools, applications about destinations, booklets given barcodes, ticket payments using QRIS (standardization of payments using the QR Code method), and already loading. The Plan for December 2022 is evaluated. Furthermore, in the PIC field, a taking team was formed, which is one hundred percent non-civil servants, so as not to be hit by working hours, one hundred percent of the age under 35 years so that the acceleration is fast, and its current performance is considered successful, both for branding Ijen Geopark, and Bondowoso Republik Kopi. Therefore, we are intensely building partnership cooperation to support institutional development, education, local economic empowerment, and digitalization..

Tirta Agung Tourism is located in the Ijen Raung KSPK Geopark, so that the spirit of development of the Tirta Agung tourism village has a connection with the development of the Ijen Geopark in the bondowoso area. In accordance with the pillars of geopark development, which include; nature and culture preservation, education, community empowerment, and tourism, the presence of Tirta Agung can be part of the development of the Ijen Bodowoso Geopark Area. Chairman of the Tourism Awareness Group, stated:

...Tirta Agung collaborates with the daily management of Ijen Geopark how to form a collaboration program to increase public awareness of tourism, preservation of the natural and cultural environment, education of young people to understand the ecology of tourism. There are so many opportunities that can be captured to become new jobs, such as the MSME movement to upgrade, marketplaces, development of village business actors, business networks, and digitalization..

Pokdarwis tirta Agung tourism village has felt the benefits of a partnership that actually provides benefits and progress of its tourism village.

CONCLUSION

Based on domain analysis which includes; (1) share vision; (2) participation (stakeholder involvement); (3) building networks (building good relationships); and (4) collaboration (stakeholder partnership management), it can be concluded that the implementation of tirta Agung tourism village in Sukosari village could run well. The implementation of the tourism village policy in Tirta Agung tourism village is able to run well through these steps: 1) Pokdarwis cooperation through the traditional communication model of local wisdom of village youth gatherings while drinking coffee is able to develop inspiration and imagination in creating innovative and creative tourist products; 2) the support of the tourism office, the daily management of the Ijen Geopark, the village triple helix component, and the penta helix element which is a partner of the local government in providing training and assistance to the village community; 3) the implementation of tourism villages is getting stronger because an adequate structure has been built between BUMDes, Pokdarwis and tourism business actors; and 4) the agreement is monitored and compliance is ensured through an evaluation conducted by the Youth and Sports Tourism Office.

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